

ASSESSMENT OF WATER DELIVERY PERFORMANCE IN CANAL COMMANDS OF KATEPURNA IRRIGATION PROJECT

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MS Received: 17.09.2025; MS Revised: 18.10.2025; MS Accepted: 19.10.2025)

MS 3450

(RESEARCH PAPER IN IRRIGATION AND DRAINAGE ENGINEERING)

Abstract

Irrigation water for agriculture is delivered by an open canal network of irrigation projects in the Maharashtra state of India. In canal network irrigation, management problems include allocation of less or excess water compared to the requirement, which results in under or over-irrigation in the command area. This study evaluates the water delivery performance of the Katepurna Irrigation Project by assessing adequacy, efficiency, equity, and dependability using data of water delivered in 27 canal outlets over five Rabi seasons (2010–2011 to 2016–2017). The study compared actual water deliveries with actual crop water requirements and analysed the temporal and spatial variations in water distribution. Results indicate significant inefficiencies, including water wastage in the early and late irrigation stages and shortages of irrigation water during peak crop water demand. The adequacy of water delivery was classified as "fair" in the Rabi seasons of 2010–2011, 2011–2012, and 2016–2017, i.e., three of the five study years and "poor" in 2012–2013 and 2013–2014. Efficiency was consistently "fair" for five years while equity and dependability indicators showed "poor" performance across multiple years. The results highlight systematic problems in the water delivery system, which indicates the need for improved irrigation scheduling and management practices to improve water use efficiency and equitable distribution. This research provides critical insights for policymakers, researchers and state irrigation department to optimise canal water management strategies in similar irrigation projects.

Keywords: Adequacy, Efficiency, Equity, Dependability, Irrigation, Agriculture

Introduction

The efficient management and proper operation of the water delivery system of irrigation projects play an important role in the sustainability of irrigated agriculture. The main objective of irrigation project management is to supply a maximum amount of water to the canal network and evacuate the excess through the drainage system. Traditional irrigation management practices have many problems which include low irrigation efficiency, uneven distribution, less canal capacity at peak water demand, etc. The low performance of the irrigation system is due to inaccurate water distribution, as there is a lack of monitoring in the water delivery system. Another reason for low irrigation performance is high conveyance losses and degradation of the canal network. To access the water delivery in the canal network, flow measurement at the delivery point is needed. Accurate management and monitoring are necessary to minimize the wastage of precious irrigation water. In India, in the past, water delivered to the canal network was not measured precisely at a minor level of the canal network, also the flow rates at the head of delivery canals were not routinely recorded. The lack of measurement in delivered water makes monitoring of irrigation efficiencies difficult. Therefore, performance assessment studies focused on water supply and water deliveries at the main canal level. It is necessary to compare irrigation water requirements with actual water delivered in the canal network to assess the performance evaluation of the canal network. Poor distribution and management of irrigation water in the water delivery system is a major factor for low efficiency and wastage of precise irrigation water hence there is a need to assess the present water delivery system performance to check whether the system is achieving its distribution aims or not. Assessment of the performance of the water delivery system describes the effectiveness of the water deliveries and operation decisions to deliver irrigation water from a reservoir. In an irrigation project, the success of the water delivery system is judged based on whether water is delivered according to the predetermined water requirement in an adequate, dependable, efficient, and equitable fashion (Molden and Gates 1990).

In India, agricultural irrigation water is delivered in open canals with a widespread distribution system of reservoirs. Water delivery is conveyed to the canals following an irrigation schedule established by the state irrigation department per the cropping pattern and water demand by water user associations and farmers. However, tail-end farmers of canal networks experience water shortages because of increasing water demand from domestic water use and industrial water use. This situation increases competition for water between sectors and necessitates more efficient use by agriculture.

Hence, the study on the assessment of water delivery performance of irrigation canals is important for identifying the key issues for water management improvement. The water delivery performance of the Katepurna Irrigation project at 27 irrigation canals during the Rabi seasons of 2010–2011, 2011–2012, 2012–2013, 2013–2014, and 2016–2017 was studied by using performance indicators adequacy, efficiency, dependability, and equity. The performance indicators were calculated from spatial and temporal distributions of estimated crop water requirement and measured water deliveries by the State Irrigation Department, District Akola, Maharashtra State, India.

Material and methods**Study area**

The main source of irrigation water for the Katepurna irrigation project is the Katepurna River. The Katepurna irrigation dam is an earthfill dam on the Katepurna River situated at Mahan, near Barshi Takli District Akola, Maharashtra, India. The Katepurna Irrigation project is located at latitude 20° 28' 53" N and longitude 77° 09' 24" E. The canal network in the Katepurna Irrigation Project consists of a main canal which is further connected to secondary canals made of concrete. The total canal network consists of 27 outlets, including the main canal, branch canals, distributaries, minors, and sub-minors. The total length of the main canal of the Katepurna irrigation project is 17.4 km, and the total length of the canal network is 122.24 km. The Total irrigated area served by these twenty-seven irrigation canal outlets is 8592 ha. In the command area of the Katepurna irrigation project, irrigation water is released only during the Rabi season, from November to March, in five irrigation rotations. The details of cropping pattern in

the five irrigation seasons 2010-2011,2011-2012,2012-2013,2013-2014and 2016-2017,except Bargaon Distributory, as this canal section did not deliver water in the study periodshown in Table 1.

Table 1 Cropping pattern of Katepurna Irrigation Project.

Crop/Year	2010-2011	2011-2012	2012-2013	2013-2014	2016-2017
Cotton	88.40	303.59	99.10	59.13	406.11
Pigeon pea	20.30	29.49	3.50	22.45	51.31
Chickpea	130.96	828.86	1599.89	2034.50	794.81
Wheat	1207.82	2062.33	1645.03	1978.56	821.13
Total area(ha)	1447.48	3224.27	3347.52	4096.64	2076.36

Determination of crop evapotranspiration and irrigation water requirement

The crop water requirement is the most important aspect of planning an irrigation schedule and rotation program in the canal command area. The month-wise crop water demand for each section of the Katepurna project was determined using the equation

$$QR = A \times WR \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$WR = ET_c - P_e \text{ ----- (2)}$$

$$ET_c = K_c \times ET_o \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Where,

QR = Volume of Irrigation water required.

A = Cropped area

WR = Irrigation water requirement of crop

ET_c = Cropevapotranspiration

P_e = Effective rainfall

K_c =Crop coefficient

ET_o =Reference cropevapotranspiration

The daily reference crop evapotranspiration for the study area was estimated using the FAO Penman-Monteith method by using 30 years (1994 to 2023) meteorological data of Akola.

Crop Coefficient

The stage-wise crop coefficient (K_c) for the crops grown in the study area was estimated following the procedure suggested by Allen et al. (FAO-56, 1998).

Effective Rainfall

The effective rainfall in the study area was estimated using a formula developed by the U.S. Department of Agriculture, Soil Conservation Service (U.S.D.A., SCS method).

$$P_{eff} = P_{month} \times (125 - 0.2 \times P_{month}) / 125 \text{ for } P_{month} \leq 250 \text{ mm}$$

$$P_{eff} = 125 + 0.1 \times P_{month} \text{ for } P_{month} > 250 \text{ mm}$$

Where,

P_{eff} = Effective Rainfall

P_{month} = Monthly Rainfall

Measurement of Water Delivered to the canal

The data regarding water delivered to each section canal (Q_D) during the canal rotation was collected from the Branch Engineer of the Palso and Bargaon Manju Branch of the Katepurna Irrigation project.

Performance Evaluation of Canal Water Delivery System

In the present study, the performance indicators viz. Adequacy (P_A), equity (P_E), Dependability (P_D), and Measure of Efficiency (P_F) have been determined to evaluate the irrigation water supply system performance (Molden and Gates, 1990).

- i. Adequacy can be defined as the ability of an irrigation system to meet the required amount of water.
- ii. Efficiency embodies the ability to conserve water by matching water deliveries with water requirements.
- iii. Equity, as related to water delivery systems, can be defined as the delivery of a fair share of water to users throughout a system.
- iv. Dependability expresses the ability to deliver water at the right time at desired place in the system.

The following equations have been used to calculate the performance indicators:

$$P_A = 1/T \sum 1/R (\sum p_A) \text{ ----- (4)}$$

$$P_F = 1/T \sum 1/R (\sum p_F) \text{ ----- (5)}$$

$$P_D = 1/R \sum CV_T (Q_D/Q_R) \text{ ----- (6)}$$

$$P_E = 1/T \sum CV_R (Q_D/Q_R) \text{ ----- (7)}$$

Where,

p_A = Q_D/Q_R if Q_D>Q_R then p_A=1

p_F = Q_R/Q_D if Q_R>Q_D then p_F=1

Q_D = Volume of water delivered

Q_R = Volume of water required

CV_T = Temporal coefficients of variation

CV_R = Spatial coefficients of variation

Table 2 Performance Standards for canal water delivery system (Molden and Gates, 1990)

Measure	Performance classes		
	Good	Fair	Poor
Adequacy P _A	0.90-1.00	0.80-0.89	<0.80
Efficiency P _F	0.85-1.00	0.70-0.84	<0.70
Equity P _E	0.00-0.10	0.11-0.25	>0.25
Dependability P _D	0.00-0.10	0.11-0.20	>0.20

Results and discussion

Spatial values of the performance indicators

Spatial average values of the adequacy (P_A), efficiency (P_F), and equity (P_E) indicators for the Katepurna Irrigation Project are shown in Fig. 1. Monthly PA and PF were computed as the average of 26 outlets. Spatial adequacy (P_A) exceeded 0.9 in November and March during the study period. P_A values of 0.88 (2010–2011) and 0.85 (2012–2013) indicated fair performance, whereas in 2011–2012 and 2016–2017 P_A ≥ 0.9 reflected good spatial adequacy. January showed consistently poor adequacy except in 2012–2013 (P_A = 0.84, fair). February adequacy remained poor (P_A < 0.8) across all years.

Spatial efficiency (P_F) was poor in November and March of 2010–2011 (P_F = 0.24 and 0.35), while December to February showed good

efficiency (P_F = 0.95–0.98). A similar pattern occurred in 2011–2012. In 2012–2013, P_F was fair in November (0.84) and poor in March (0.55), but remained good (>0.85) in the mid-season months. In 2013–2014, P_F was good from November to February (>0.85), but poor in March (0.03). In 2016–2017, efficiency was fair in November and good in December–February, with fair performance in March. Equity (P_E) performance was largely poor, with P_E > 0.25 in 2010–2011, 2013–2014, and 2016–2017. Only in 2012–2013 and 2013–2014 did spatial PE fall within 0.11–0.25, indicating fair equity performance.

a) Adequacy

c) Equity

Fig.1 Comparison of spatial values of the performance indicators a. Adequacy b. Efficiency c. Equity**Temporal values of the performance indicators**

Table 3 represents the average adequacy values of all locations from where actual water is allocated to the farmers. The adequacy performance was found in the good category in 14 out of 26 canal sections in the year 2010-11 viz MC, SSM, BBC, BD, GM, RM, PaM, SAM, MD, PSM, DAM, and BHD. In 8 sections TM, DM, PM, KM, DHM-1, BM-1, BM-2, MM adequacy performance was found to be fair as the adequacy was below 0.89 and more than 0.8. Three sections i.e. TEM, SM and DAM showed poor adequacy performance as the adequacy values were found below 0.8.

In the years 2011-2012, 13 sections PM, BM-1, BM-2, SM, SSM, BBC, RM, DHM, NM, MM, PaM, SAM and DAM obtained in good category class of adequacy performance indicator. Whereas 9 sections

viz TM, DM, KM, BD, GM, MD, KUM, PSM, and BHD were shown a fair adequacy performance as the values of P_A ranged between 0.8 to 0.89. The canal sections MC, DHM-1, TEM and HM showed a poor adequacy performance as the $P_A < 0.8$. In the year 2012-2013, 6 canal sections, PM, SSM, RM, DHM, NM and RM showed a good adequacy performance as $P_A > 0.9$. Whereas 16 sections showed a fair adequacy performance as the P_A values were ranged between 0.8 to 0.89. Remaining 4 canal sections delivered inadequate water as compared to the requirement of crops, because the P_A values were below 0.8 which results in the poor delivery performance of canal sections. The canal sections which were poor in the delivery of canal water are MC, DHM-1, TEM and BM-1.

Table 3: Temporal Adequacy indicator values of the Katepurna irrigation project

S.N.	Canal Section	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2016-17
1	Main Canal (MC)	0.91	0.79	0.74	0.62	0.99
2	Bahadarpur Branch Canal (BBC)	0.86	0.85	0.84	0.79	0.11
3	Tamsi minor(TM)	0.84	0.86	0.87	0.8	0.2
4	Dhagam minor(DM)	0.83	0.91	0.96	1	0.95
5	Pailpada minor (PM)	0.84	0.87	0.86	0.44	0.88
6	Khadka minor(KM)	0.86	0.65	0.6	0.66	0.92
7	Dahigaon minor 1 (DM-1)	0.68	0.61	0.52	0.56	0.79
8	Telkhed minor TEM	0.84	0.92	0.75	0.71	0.99
9	Borgaon minor 1 (BM-1)	0.88	0.96	0.86	0.83	1
10	Borgaon minor 2 (BM-2)	0.75	0.97	0.88	0.75	0.98
11	Sultanpur minor (SM)	0.94	0.97	0.91	0.8	1
12	Sultanpur sub minor(SSM)	0.96	0.91	0.88	0.82	0.87
13	Bahirkhed Distributory (BD)	0.92	0.81	0.86	0.79	0.91
14	Gondapur minor (GM)	1	0.88	0.86	0.82	0.81
15	Ramgaon minor (RM)	0.98	0.91	0.9	0.82	1
16	Dahigaon minor (DHM)	--	0.9	0.97	0.81	0.92
17	Nawkhed minor (NM)	--	0.94	0.93	0.8	0.89
18	Majalapur minor (MM)	0.82	0.92	0.94	0.85	1
19	Palso minor (PaM)	0.97	0.91	0.86	0.82	0.86
20	Shahapur minor (SAM)	0.95	1	0.85	0.83	0.83
21	Mahamadpur Distributory(MD)	0.93	0.89	0.87	0.82	0.86
22	Kaulkhed minor (KUM)	0.31	0.88	0.89	0.82	0.8
23	Pared, Sangwa minor (PSM)	0.91	0.88	0.89	0.83	0.81
24	Hasanpur minor (HM)	--	0.78	0.88	0.8	0.77
25	Datala minor (DAM)	0.93	0.9	0.86	0.84	0.78

26	BhatoriDistributory (BHD)	1	0.89	0.84	0.82	0.87
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In 2013-2014 canal section PM delivered sufficient water as the P_A value was found to be 1, which results in a good adequacy performance class and 8 canal sections had a P_A value less than 0.8 which shows a poor adequacy performance and remaining 17 sections P_A values were ranged between 0.8 to 0.89 shows a fair performance. In 2016-2017 11 canal sections viz MC, PM, DHM-1, BM-1, BM-2, SM, SSM, BD, RM, DHM, and MM, adequacy performance was found to be good as the $P_A \geq 0.9$. While fair performance was found in 10 sections (KM, BBC, GM, NM, PaM, SAM, MD, KUM, PSM, and BHD) as the P_A values ranged between 0.89-0.8 and remaining 5 sections (TM, DM, TEM, HM and DAM) P_A values were below 0.79 indicates a poor performance.

The temporal efficiency performance of the Katepurna Irrigation project is presented in Table 4. In the 2010-2011 canal section, KUM performed good as the $P_F = 1$. Nine sections viz DM, PM, KM, DHM-1, TEM, BM-1, SM, SSM and MM showed fair performance of the efficiency as the values of P_F were between 0.7 to 0.85. Whereas the 13 section (MC, TM, BM-2, BBC, BD, GM, RM, PaM, SAM, MD, PSM DAM and BHD.) shows a poor temporal efficiency performance as the P_F values are less than 0.7

In 2011-2012 two section DHM-1 and TEM utilized water efficiently as the P_F value was 0.9. Section SAM showed a poor efficiency performance as the value of P_F was 0.65. while the remaining 24

sections showed a fair temporal efficiency performance as the P_F values ranged between 0.7 and 0.84.

In 2012-2013, 19 sections performed good in the case of temporal efficiency as P_F values were ranged between 0.85 to 1, while the 7 sections (KM, BM-2, KUM, DAM, PM, DHM and BHD) showed a fair efficiency performance, as the P_F values ranged between 0.7 to 0.85.

In 2013-2014 no section had good temporal efficiency. Only one section PM showed a poor temporal efficiency as P_F values were 0.38 and remaining 25 sections shown a fair temporal efficiency performance as P_F values were ranges between 0.7-0.84.

In 2016-2017, $P_F = 1$ in two sections TM and DM, which resulted in good temporal efficiency performance. 17 sections have P_F values in the range of 0.7-0.84, which indicates a fair temporal efficiency performance. The remaining 7 sections, MC, BM-1, BM-2, SM, SSM, RM, and MM, showed a poor performance of temporal efficiency as the P_F values were less than 0.7

Table 5 represent the dependability performance indicator of the Katepurna irrigation project canal network. The temporal coefficient variation in ratio Q_D/Q_R over the time period November to March shows a result that there was a poor dependability performance in all five years.

Table 4: Temporal Efficiency indicator values of the Katepurna irrigation project

S.N.	Canal Section	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2016-17
1	Main Canal (MC)	0.69	0.88	0.92	0.8	0.68
2	Bahadarpur Branch Canal (BBC)	0.69	0.88	0.93	0.81	1
3	Tamsi minor(TM)	0.73	0.88	0.9	0.81	1
4	Dhagaminor(DM)	0.7	0.8	0.76	0.38	0.79
5	Pailpada minor (PM)	0.7	0.81	0.84	0.8	0.81
6	Khadka minor(KM)	0.7	0.96	0.97	0.8	0.79
7	Dahigaon minor 1 (DM-1)	0.82	1	1	0.81	0.92
8	Telkhed minor TEM	0.7	0.85	0.93	0.8	0.72
9	Borgaon minor 1 (BM-1)	0.69	0.77	0.84	0.77	0.66
10	Borgaon minor 2 (BM-2)	0.77	0.8	0.87	0.81	0.71
11	Sultanpur minor (SM)	0.74	0.79	0.87	0.81	0.58
12	Sultanpur sub minor(SSM)	0.66	0.79	0.86	0.79	0.85
13	BahirkhedDistributory (BD)	0.69	0.87	0.87	0.8	0.79
14	Gondapur minor (GM)	0.58	0.82	0.88	0.79	0.9
15	Ramgaon minor (RM)	0.65	0.78	0.87	0.8	0.69
16	Dahigaon minor (DHM)	--	0.84	0.72	0.81	0.85
17	Nawkhed minor (NM)	--	0.8	0.9	0.81	0.87
18	Majalapur minor (MM)	0.78	0.78	0.85	0.81	0.75
19	Palso minor (PaM)	0.65	0.79	0.9	0.8	0.9
20	Shahapur minor (SAM)	0.66	0.65	0.87	0.77	0.87
21	MahamadpurDistributory(MD)	0.67	0.8	0.88	0.79	0.88
22	Kaulkhed minor (KUM)	1	0.81	0.84	0.79	0.9
23	Pared, Sangwa minor (PSM)	0.68	0.81	0.86	0.78	0.87
24	Hasanpur minor (HM)	--	0.85	0.91	0.81	0.96
25	Datala minor (DAM)	0.67	0.79	0.84	0.77	0.89
26	BhatoriDistributory (BHD)	0.49	0.8	0.84	0.8	0.89

Table 5: Dependability indicator (P_D) values of the Katepurna irrigation project

S.N.	Canal Section	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2016-17
1	Main Canal (MC)	0.91	0.59	0.55	2.11	0.53
2	Bahadarpur Branch Canal (BBC)	1.98	0.43	0.35	1.88	0.42
3	Tamsi minor(TM)	2.87	0.41	0.37	1.99	0.38
4	Dhagaminor(DM)	3.94	0.56	0.57	2.13	0.65
5	Pailpada minor (PM)	5.01	0.62	0.56	2.16	0.52
6	Khadka minor(KM)	6.03	0.49	0.50	2.11	0.57
7	Dahigaon minor 1 (DM-1)	6.86	0.43	0.41	1.93	0.43
8	Telkhed minor TEM	7.93	0.51	0.49	2.12	0.57

9	Borgaon minor 1 (BM-1)	8.88	0.59	0.56	2.21	0.59
10	Borgaon minor 2 (BM-2)	9.70	0.49	0.48	2.02	0.45
11	Sultanpur minor (SM)	10.23	0.45	0.44	1.89	0.48
12	Sultanpur sub minor (SSM)	11.23	0.58	0.47	2.02	0.53
13	Bahirkhed Distributory (BD)	12.17	0.56	0.49	2.05	0.51
14	Gondapur minor (GM)	12.99	0.50	0.46	2.00	0.44
15	Ramgaon minor (RM)	13.85	0.58	0.44	1.99	0.59
16	Dahigaon minor (DHM)	--	0.39	0.37	1.88	0.39
17	Nawkhed minor (NM)	--	0.48	0.36	1.88	0.43
18	Majalapur minor (MM)	14.49	0.61	0.36	1.96	0.59
19	Palso minor (PaM)	15.42	0.58	0.41	1.97	0.42
20	Shahapur minor (SAM)	16.44	0.54	0.50	2.16	0.49
21	Mahamadpur Distributory(MD)	17.52	0.57	0.45	2.00	0.44
22	Kaulkhed minor (KUM)	18.59	0.57	0.50	2.03	0.44
23	Pared, Sangwa minor (PSM)	19.66	0.57	0.44	2.10	0.50
24	Hasanpur minor (HM)	--	0.62	0.35	1.87	0.38
25	Datala minor (DAM)	20.74	0.62	0.58	2.17	0.48
26	Bhatori Distributory (BHD)	21.58	0.57	0.61	1.96	0.41

Average values of the performance indicator

The average values of the adequacy, efficiency, equity and dependability indicators of the Katepurna Irrigation project canal network are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Water delivery performance values of the canal network of the Katepurna Irrigation Project

Year/Performance indicator	Adequacy (P _A)	Efficiency (P _F)	Equity (P _E)	Dependability (P _D)
2010-2011	0.87	0.7	0.33	0.94
2011-2012	0.87	0.82	0.22	0.53
2012-2013	0.85	0.87	0.2	0.46
2013-2014	0.78	0.78	0.59	2.02
2016-2017	0.84	0.83	0.39	0.49

During 2010-2011, considering performance standards given by Molden and Gates (1990), adequacy (0.87) and efficiency(0.70) indicators of the project were found in the range of "fair" performance class. Whereas equity(0.33) and dependability(0.94) indicators were obtained in the range of "poor" performance class. Similarly, in 2011-2012, the adequacy (0.87) was "fair" performance as per the performance standard Table 2. The average Efficiency (0.82) was a "fair" efficiency performance. The average Equity (0.22) was a "fair" performance of the Equity indicator. The average Dependability (0.94) indicates a "poor" dependability performance as per the performance standard.

In 2012-2013 adequacy (0.85) indicates a "poor" performance of adequacy and efficiency (0.87) indicates a "good" performance of efficiency, whereas the equity(0.23) which shows a "fair" performance of equity. Dependability (0.73) indicates a much greater variation in water deliveries in canal network and dependability performance was "poor".

The adequacy(0.78) in 2013-2014 indicates an inadequate water supply in the canal network and results in a "poor" performance class. The efficiency(0.78) indicates a "fair" performance in terms of the efficiency indicator. The equity (0.59) and dependability (2.02) values were greater than 0.25 and 0.2, as per the performance standard table, these values are categorized as a "poor" performance of the Equity and Dependability indicator.

In 2016-2017 adequacy (0.84) and efficiency(0.83), both were in the range of "fair" performance class as per table 3. The Equity (0.39) and Dependability(0.49) values were more than 0.25 and 0.2 which were categorized as a "poor" performance of equity and dependability indicators of the water delivery system of the Katepurna Irrigation project.

Conclusion

The study revealed that the water delivery system of the Katepurna Irrigation Project shows considerable variation in adequacy,

efficiency, equity, and dependability across years and canal sections. While adequacy and efficiency mostly fell in the "fair" category, equity and dependability consistently showed "poor" performance, indicating uneven and unreliable water distribution. These results highlight operational issues such as improper scheduling, conveyance losses, and inadequate monitoring. Improving flow measurement, strengthening canal maintenance, and adopting better irrigation scheduling practices are essential for enhancing the overall performance and achieving more reliable and equitable water delivery in the command area.

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